

2016

Study of Inmates in the Bahamas

Rodolfo Sarsfield & Marcelo Bergman

CELIV

Center for Latin American
Studies on Crime and Violence

Study of Inmates in the Bahamas

Rodolfo Sarsfield & Marcelo Bergman

Assitant: Guadalupe Peralta Agüero

Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero (UNTREF)/ International Development Bank (IDB)/
Center for Latin American Studies on Crime and Violence (CELIV), 2016

Contents

Tables Index.....	v
Figures Index	ix
Acknowledgements.....	xi
SUMMARY.....	xii
CHAPTER ONE: CHILDHOOD AND LIFE STORY	1
Childhood	1
Level of education	7
Use of drugs	10
Inmates and children.....	13
Criminal background at the family	15
Classmates	16
Inmates' context before being arrested for the first time.....	17
Financial position, satisfaction with economic situation, and job status prior to arrest	19
CHAPTER 2: CRIMINAL CAREERS AND INMATES' PROFILES: RECIDIVISM, VIOLENT CRIME, AND SERIOUS FELONIES	26
The first time for being arrested.....	27
Criminal Career and Recidivism.....	28
Alcohol or drugs and recidivism	29
Criminogenic context during the childhood and recidivism	30
Violent crime.....	33
Serious felonies.....	36
CHAPTER THREE: DUE PROCESS.....	39
Inmates' legal situation.....	39
Time for the arrest.....	39
Police treatment	40
Criminal justice treatment.....	42
Corruption and criminal justice.....	50
CHAPTER FOUR: THE CONDITIONS IN THE PRISON	51
Accommodation and hygiene conditions.....	51
Activities and entertainments into the prison	59
Treatment to relatives and economy of the visit to the prison	60

Study of Inmates in the Bahamas
Investigation Report

► R.Sarsfield & M. Bergman

Corruption into the prison..... 62

Conjugal visits and sexual life of inmates 64

Safety in prison..... 67

Alcohol and drugs inside the prison 68

Getting drugs and substances..... 70

Activities and programs for social reintegration in the prison 71

Beyond the prison: life after being released..... 75

FINAL REMARKS..... 79

APPENDIX..... 84

REFERENCES 86

Tables Index

Table 1.....	1
Table 2.....	2
Table 3.....	2
Table 4.....	3
Table 5.....	4
Table 6.....	4
Table 7.....	5
Table 8.....	5
Table 9.....	5
Table 10.....	6
Table 11.....	7
Table 12.....	7
Table 13.....	8
Table 14.....	10
Table 15.....	10
Table 16.....	11
Table 17.....	12
Table 18.....	13
Table 19.....	14
Table 20.....	14
Table 21.....	14
Table 22.....	15
Table 23.....	17
Table 24.....	17
Table 25.....	18
Table 26.....	20
Table 27.....	20
Table 28.....	21
Table 29.....	21
Table 30.....	22
Table 31.....	23
Table 32.....	23

Table 33.....	28
Table 34.....	29
Table 35.....	29
Table 36.....	30
Table 37.....	30
Table 38.....	31
Table 39.....	31
Table 40.....	32
Table 41.....	32
Table 42.....	33
Table 43.....	34
Table 44.....	34
Table 45.....	35
Table 46.....	35
Table 47.....	36
Table 48.....	37
Table 49.....	37
Table 50.....	37
Table 51.....	38
Table 52.....	38
Table 53.....	40
Table 54.....	41
Table 55.....	41
Table 56.....	41
Table 57.....	41
Table 58.....	42
Table 59.....	42
Table 60.....	43
Table 61.....	44
Table 62.....	44
Table 63.....	45
Table 64.....	46
Table 65.....	46
Table 66.....	47

Table 67	47
Table 68	48
Table 69	48
Table 70	49
Table 71	50
Table 72	51
Table 73	52
Table 74	55
Table 75	55
Table 76	56
Table 77	56
Table 78	57
Table 79	57
Table 80	58
Table 81	58
Table 82	59
Table 83	60
Table 84	61
Table 85	61
Table 86	62
Table 87	63
Table 88	64
Table 89	64
Table 90	65
Table 91	65
Table 92	66
Table 93	66
Table 94	67
Table 95	67
Table 96	68
Table 97	68
Table 98	69
Table 99	69
Table 100	70

Study of Inmates in the Bahamas
Investigation Report

→ R.Sarsfield & M. Bergman

Table 101	72
Table 102	72
Table 103	73
Table 104	74
Table 105	75
Table 106	76
Table 107	76
Table 108	77
Table 109	77
Table 110	78
Table 111	78

Figures Index

Figure 1.....	9
Figure 2.....	11
Figure 3.....	12
Figure 4.....	13
Figure 5.....	15
Figure 6.....	16
Figure 7.....	16
Figure 8.....	18
Figure 9.....	19
Figure 10.....	24
Figure 11.....	26
Figure 12.....	27
Figure 13.....	28
Figure 14.....	33
Figure 15.....	39
Figure 16.....	44
Figure 17.....	49
Figure 18.....	50
Figure 19.....	51
Figure 20.....	52
Figure 21.....	53
Figure 22.....	53
Figure 23.....	54
Figure 24.....	54
Figure 25.....	56
Figure 26.....	58
Figure 27.....	59
Figure 28.....	63
Figure 29.....	67
Figure 30.....	70
Figure 31.....	71
Figure 32.....	73
Figure 33.....	74

Figure 34 75

Acknowledgements

This study could not have been done without the kind assistance of William Fielding at The College of Bahamas, the cooperation of the members of the Parole and Probation Committee, and the staff of the Department of Corrections, in Nassau, Bahamas. Hernán Flom and Lina Marmolejo (IDB) assisted to The College of Bahamas in the preparation of the fieldwork.

Guadalupe Peralta Agüero assisted with the preparation of the tables for this report and María de la Paz Arias kindly edited this work.

The following persons assisted with the data collection at The Bahamas Department of Correctional Services at Fox Hill: Richard Adderley, Andrea Archer, Andrella Dames, Dr. Niambi Hall-Campbell, Jordan Hutcheson, Dr. Stephanie Hutcheson, Jennifer Isaacs-Dotson, Jessica Minnis, Yvette Pintard-Newry, Wendy Poitier-Albury, Cheyenne Symonette, and E'Thegra Symonette.

Financial support for this project was provided by the IDB.

SUMMARY

- Childhood and Life Story:

Seven out of ten inmates were physically punished by either their parents or guardians when interns were children.

In three out of ten inmates' households, the father or the mother's partner beat her/his mother.

More than one out of two every inmates lived in single-parent households when they were children. Even more, findings suggest that a significant share of the inmates have lived without any of their parents since an early age.

Findings showing that a good part of the inmates' mothers had to work in low incomes jobs and time-demanding jobs. This suggests a causal path between low levels of social control at home when at early childhood and ulterior deviant behavior.

Inmates living in a criminogenic territorial context when they were children matter. In half of the cases, the inmates' best friends had committed crimes when those were kids. In a similar way, the majority of the inmates said there were gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where they lived as minors

Results show that most inmates started to work at an early age: one of every four of those inmates worked for the first time for pay when they were only twelve years old or less, and one in two of those inmates worked for the first time when they were fifteen years old or less. Additionally, nine out of ten interns started to work when they were eighteen years old or less.

Most inmates were very young when they become parents.

Six out of every ten inmates have a family member that has been sent to prison before.

Findings on the context in which inmates were arrested suggest, in general terms, that such context wasn't a cause of the inmates' arrest. When we compare these findings with the

results on the context during the inmates' childhood, it seems that infancy is more important than the context in which the inmates lived before being arrested in order to explain their antisocial behavior.

Relative deprivation theory does not seem to explain criminal behavior in the Bahamas. Most inmates felt that they were in a "better" or in a "much better" financial position than their close immediate circle of friends before being arrested for the crime they serve now.

Although most inmates were working before detention, results show that they had hard job conditions for a good portion of the inmates one month before they were arrested.

- **Criminal career:**

Most inmates were arrested for the first time when they were very young.

There are both similar and dissimilar patterns to explain different profiles of the criminal careers among inmates.

Recidivism seems to be related with the consumption of illegal drugs.

Recidivism seems to be linked with a family in which there is someone that had been sent to the prison.

Recidivism seems to be related to violence at home during the inmates' childhood.

Friends with some type of criminal behavior at the inmates' childhood seem to be a strong predictor of recidivism.

In general terms, recidivism seems to be related with an inmate's childhood developed in a criminogenic context.

There is no relationship between relative deprivation (the inmates' perceived situation compared with others) and recidivism.

Violent crime is related with the use of alcohol and/or drugs during the six hours prior to commit the crime.

Violent crime seems to be related with inmates' childhood in a criminogenic social context.

Findings suggest that to commit a serious felony as an adult is related with the presence of gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where the inmates lived when they were minors.

It seems there is a relationship between inmates that committed a serious felony and families with a criminal background.

- Due process:

The legal situation of the inmates is mixed, although seven out of ten interns are sentenced inmates.

A large share part of the inmates were probably arrested "red-handed" or in flagrante. This finding suggests that those offenders that were not arrested at the time they committed the crime are more likely to not being arrested at all.

Nine out of ten inmates were never shown a warrant in writing by the police.

Of those inmates that were taken to the police station, six out of ten inmates were not informed that they were entitled to make a phone call. Additionally, one out of two inmates was not informed at the police station that they were entitled to a lawyer.

One out of two inmates was hit or someone used physical force against them to compel them to testify or to change their statement while they were at the police station.

In one out of two cases, the magistrate was not present when the inmates made their preliminary statement. Also, in seven out of every ten cases, the inmates report their lawyers were not present when the interns made their preliminary statement.

Six out of ten inmates were not informed they had the right to remain silent during their preliminary statement. Also, seven out of ten inmates were not informed during their preliminary statement that if they pleaded guilty they could get a reduced sentence.

Four out of ten inmates didn't understand what was happening at the hearings in court.

One third of the inmates said they had never spoken to the judge directly.

One out of four inmates didn't have a lawyer from their arrest until they were sentenced.

One out of two inmates thinks that their lawyers defended them "little", "very little", or "not at all".

Only 2.4% of the inmates received support from a human rights groups or organization between their arrest and the end of the trial.

Of those inmates that were transferred from one prison to another before being sentenced on the first instance, one out of two inmates was transferred farther away from where their families live.

- The conditions in the prison:

Six out of ten inmates said that in their prison cells sleep more inmates that they should.

In most cases, accommodation and hygiene items are provided by the inmates' families and not by the prison.

Four out of every ten inmates think the toilets they use are dirty or very dirty.

Nine out of every ten inmates think the quality of the food they receive is poor or very poor.

The majority of the inmates think that the amount of food they receive is insufficient.

Half of the inmates think that the drinking water they receive is enough but it tastes bad.

When inmates get sick, most of them receive medical care, although only one out of every ten is satisfied with such care.

In eight out of every ten cases, the prison provides the medicines the inmates need.

Most inmates have access to the radio, have access to a public phone, have access to books, have access to newspapers, and have access to magazines.

Most inmates said that they cannot watch TV, and the vast majority of the inmates said they have access neither to a PC nor to the internet.

Four out of ten inmates think their relatives or partner are treated relatively well when they come to visit them.

Six out of ten inmates said their families give them between one and one hundred dollars each time they visit them.

One third of the inmates said it takes between two and five hours to their families to visit them.

Four out of ten inmates spend more than one hundred dollars by month inside prisons.

Findings seem to support that there is not corruption in the prison: a vast majority of inmates said their families don't have to pay for entering the prison or don't have to pay for bringing them food or other items.

Regarding the perceptions on corruption to obtain an undue pre-release, 42% of the interns think that no inmate has paid to obtain it.

Regarding the intimate visit, and over the past six months, nine out of ten inmates have not received any conjugal visit.

When interns were asked about whether in the past six months they had had sexual relations with any person other than their spouse or partner, a vast majority of the inmates answered “No”.

Nine out of ten inmates said that they have not witnessed another inmate being forced to have sexual intercourse with other people.

98.8% of the inmates said they were not forced to have sexual intercourse against their will since they were arrested.

Eight out of ten inmates feel less safe at prison compared to their home or the place where they lived before.

Most of the inmates said that someone has stolen their personal belongings inside the prison facility.

Eight out of ten inmates said they have seen another inmate being beaten.

Seven out of ten inmates have seen other inmates using alcohol and/or drugs.

Findings suggest that the use of alcohol and soft drugs prevails over the use of hard drugs into the prison.

Half of the inmates think it is either “very easy” or “easy” to get drugs and substances into the prison.

Seven out of ten inmates believes that the prison staffs are the ones who brings more drugs into the prison facilities.

Only one out of every four inmates thinks that the education programs the prison offers are either “good” or “very good”.

Only 14.0% of the inmates are satisfied with the assistance given by psychologists and social workers in the prison.

Inmates’ participation in entertainment activities in the prison –such as sport activities–, is low.

Six out of ten inmates perform some kind of work inside prisons. One third of those inmates said they received a payment for the work they performed.

Seven out of ten inmates think that their lives will be better after they will be released from the prison. However, most inmates are also afraid of some issues such as not finding a job, being rejected by their families, being re-arrested, or either getting sick or developing an addiction.

CHAPTER ONE: CHILDHOOD AND LIFE STORY

Childhood

Living conditions during the infancy for a good part of the prisoners seem to have been conducive to the development of antisocial behavior. According to the responses of an important part of the inmates, it can be claimed that interns were exposed to different criminogenic contexts when they were children. Among these contexts, inmates said that they had been victims of violence in their home, that they had lived in neighborhoods with gangs or criminal groups when they were minors, and/or they have had friends during their childhood who committed crimes.

When inmates were children, a vast majority of them were usually punished with violence by either their parents or guardians (78.2%), 6.4% were punished in some cases, and only 15.4% of respondents were not physically punished by them (Table 1). In other words, in the majority of the cases (84.6%), inmates were physically punished by their parents or guardians to some degree when they were children. Additionally, outcomes show that inmates' father or mother's partner used to beat/hit their mothers in two out of ten respondents (18.9%) and 16.1% of the inmates' father or mother's partner beat their mothers "sometimes" (Table 2). Therefore, findings indicate that there was some kind of intra home violence in a large share of the cases (35%) when inmates were children.

Table 1

When you were little, did either of your parents or your guardians physically punish you?		
	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Yes	78.2%	78.2%
In some cases	6.4%	84.6%
No	15.4%	100%
Total	100%	100%

N = 367

Table 2

Do you know whether your father or mother's partner ever beat/hit your mother?		
	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Yes, he used to beat her	18.9%	18.9%
Sometimes he beat her	16.1%	35%
No, he didn't beat her	47.5%	82.5%
Other	1.4%	83.9%
DK/NA	16.1%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

When the inmates were children (until aged 18), their father was most likely to have been self-employed or working as one of the lower paid occupations (Table 3). The employment of fathers focused on two main activities, “Self-employed/Taxi driver/Driver/Street vendor/Craftsman” (19.9%) and “Construction worker/Factory worker” (19.7 %). Also, 7.2% of the inmates’ father worked as farmer or fisherman, 6.1% worked in the hotel industry, and 2.8% worked as handyman or gardener. In other words, six out of ten of the inmates’ fathers, worked in lower paid occupations when those inmates were children.

Table 3

When you were a child (until 18), which was your father's main occupation?	
	Valid Percentage
Professional	3.6%
Civil servant	8.3%
Company employee	15.2%
Hotel industry	6.1%
Construction worker/Factory worker	19.7%
Self-employed/Taxi driver/Driver/Street vendor/Craftsman	19.9%
Executive/Manager	0.6%

Farmer/fisherman	7.2%
Handyman/gardener	2.8%
He did not work	2.8%
Other	2.8%
DK/NA	11.1%
Total	100%

N = 367

Results (Table 4) also show that a vast majority of the mothers worked when inmates were young (86.4%). As in the case of the fathers, a large share (or a significant part) of the inmates' mothers worked in one of the lower paid jobs: 21.0% worked as self-employed/street vendor/seamstress/craftswoman/driver, 17.1% worked as maid, and 13% worked in the hotel industry (Table 5). Since these types of jobs are time-demanding, both findings may suggest a possible link between a lower level of social control at home when inmates were children and ulterior criminal behavior.

Table 4

When you were a child, did your mother used to work?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	86.4%
No	6.9%
Sometimes	0.8%
DK/NA	5.8%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 5

Which was your mother's main occupation?	
	Valid Percent
Professional	2.5%
Civil servant	15.2%
Company employee	27.6%
Hotel industry	13%
Housewife	0.3%
Construction/Factory worker	1.3%
Self-employed/Street vendor/Seamstress/Craftswoman/Driver	21%
Executive/Manager	0.6%
Maid	17.1%
Farmer/fisherwoman	1%
DK/NA	0.3%
Total	100%

N = 315

(This question does not apply to inmates that said their mother did not use to work)

Contrarily to what it is often assumed, in the vast majority of the cases, the inmates' parents or adults with whom they lived, did not drink alcohol frequently (61.8%) or used drugs when the inmates were very young (83.3%)(see Table 6 and Table 7).

Table 6

Did either of your parents or any of the adults you lived with when you were a child use to drink alcohol frequently?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	36.5%
No	61.8%
DK/NA	1.7%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 7

Did either of your parents or any of the adults you lived with when you were a child use to do illegal drugs?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	15.3%
No	83.3%
DK/NA	1.4%
Total	100%

N = 367

Inmates living in a criminogenic territorial context when they were children do matter. In half of the cases (47.8%), the inmates' best friends had committed some crime when those were kids (Table 8). In a similar way, the majority of the inmates (53.5%) said there were gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where they grew up as minors (Table 9).

Table 8

Before you turned 18, did you know whether any of your best friends committed any crimes, either one or several from time to time?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	47.8%
No	48.0%
DK/NA	4.2%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 9

Could you please tell me whether there were gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where you lived as a minor (Under 18 years)?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	53.5%
No	43.5%
DK/NA	3.1%
Total	100%

N = 367

At the same time, half of the inmates' parents did not lived together (51%) when inmates were children –and 2.8% of the parents did so only some of the time (Table 10). In other words, more than half of the inmates lived in broken homes when they were children. On the other hand, 18.8% of the inmates said they had lived with their mother only until they became fifteen years old or less (Table 11). This rate increases to 44.8% if considering the percentage of inmates that lived with their mothers up to eighteen years old. Similarly, a large share of inmates lived with their father until a comparatively premature age (Table 12): only the 19 % of the inmates said they lived with their fathers until they became fifteen years old or less and 34.5% did so until they were eighteen years old or less. The combination of these findings suggests that an important portion of inmates have lived in single-parental households or, even more, without any of their parents since an early age. These results suggest there might be some relationship between the kind of inmates' household and deviant behavior. ¹

Table 10

During that period, did your parents live together?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	43.5%
No	51%
Some of the time	2.8%
DK/NA	2.8%
Total	100%

N = 367

¹ It is worth to mention that in six out of ten violent crimes, the offender had grew up in a broken home (see Appendix, Table 1).

Table 11

Up to what age did you live with your mother?		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1 to 6 years	3.9%	3.9%
7 to 12 years	4.7%	8.6%
13 to 15 years	10.2%	18.8%
16 to 18 years	26%	44.8%
19 years or more	45.4%	90.2%
Never lived with his/her mother	7.8%	98%
DK/NA	1.9%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Table 12

Up to what age did you live with your father?		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1 to 6 years	5.4%	5.4%
7 to 12 years	7.1%	12.5%
13 to 15 years	6.5%	19%
16 to 18 years	15.5%	34.5%
19 years or more	23.4%	57.9%
Never lived with his/her mother	35.3%	93.2%
DK/NA	6.8%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Level of education

The highest level of education reached before being arrested for the first time was incomplete high school or a lower level of education for 62.1% of inmates (Table 13). At the same time, the mean age whereby inmates' attended school last time was 16.72 years old (the median was 16 years old) (Figure 1). From both findings we can infer that most of inmates left the school at a premature age.

Table 13

What level of education had you reached before being arrested the first time?		
	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Did not attend school	0.3%	0.3%
Incomplete primary	2.2%	2.5%
Complete primary	0.3%	2.8%
Incomplete junior school	12%	14.8%
Complete junior school	4.5%	19.2%
Incomplete high school	42.9%	62.1%
Complete high school	25.6%	87.7%
Tech Voc training (BTVI etc.)	3.9%	91.6%
Incomplete university/college	3.9%	95.5%
Complete university/college or further studies	3.9%	99.4%
DK/NA	0.6%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Figure 1

How old were you when you went to school for the last time?

N: 367

Considering the age of the inmates when they had their first job for pay, one out of four inmates (24.9%) worked when they were only twelve years old or less. Even more, half of those inmates (53.9%) worked for the first time when they were fifteen years old or less (Table 14). Additionally, data show that 91.4 % of inmates worked when they were eighteen years old or less. *These results show that a vast majority of inmates started to work at an early age.* The combination of having to leave the school and having to start working when they were very young, to be sure, affected their lives and their structures of opportunities. These patterns of their life when they were young may explain in part their paths to crime and prison.

Table 14

At what age did you work for the first time for pay?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated percentage
1 to 12 years	24.9%	24.9%
13 to 15 years	29%	53.9%
16 to 18 years	37.5%	91.4%
19 or more years	8.7%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Use of drugs

Regarding the use of illegal drugs, 69.4% of the inmates said they had consumed it at some point in their lives (Table 15).

Table 15

Have you ever consumed an illegal drug?	
	Valid Percentage
No	30.6%
Yes	69.4%
Total	100%

N = 367

When inmates were asked about which drug they had used, findings show that marijuana and base paste/cocaine/crack are the two most popular drugs. Considering the use of marijuana, 63.5% of the interns said they had consumed it in the past. Regarding the use of base paste/cocaine/crack, 9% of the inmates told they had used one of them. 6.5% of the inmates said they had consumed pills/ecstasy in the past. Finally, 0.8% of the interns told they had used inhalants, 0.5% said they had consumed heroin, and 1.4% of the inmates told they had used other drugs.

Figure 2

N = 238

(This question is not applicable for those interns that said they did not consume an illegal drug)
Multiple responses are allowed

Regarding the two drugs more used among inmates, marijuana and cocaine or crack, results show that in both cases interns started to consume them at an early age. Considering the age of those inmates that started to use marijuana, half of those interns (51.5%) began using it when they were fifteen years old or less (Table 16). A large majority of those inmates (83.5%) started using marijuana when they were eighteen years old or less (Table 16), being seventeen (17) the mode age (Figure 16). Regarding the use of base paste/cocaine/crack, one out of four of those inmates (24.2%) started using them when they were fifteen years old or less (Table 17). The mode was twenty-one years old (and the minimum age was nine years old) (Figure 3).

Table 16

Marijuana		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1 to 15 years	51.5%	51.5%
16 to 18 years	32%	83.5%
19 to 21 years	7.4%	90.9%
22 to 25 years	5.2%	96.1%
26 to 32 years	3.5%	99.6%
33 to 40 years	0.4%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 231

(This question is not applicable for those interns that said they did not consume marijuana)

Figure 3

At what age did you start using Marijuana?

Age of those inmates that consumed marijuana (N= 231)

(This question is not applicable for those interns that said they did not consume an illegal drug)

Mode: 17 years

Table 17

Cocaine/ base paste/ crack		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1 to 15 years	24.2%	24.2%
16 to 18 years	9.1%	33.3%
19 to 21 years	21.2%	54.5%
22 to 25 years	12.1%	66.7%
26 to 32 years	24.2%	90.9%
33 to 40 years	9.1%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 33

(This question is not applicable for those interns that said they did not consume cocaine/base paste/crack)

Figure 4

At what age did you start using Cocaine base paste/cocaine/ crack?

Age of those inmates that consumed cocaine base paste/cocaine/crack (N= 33)
(This question is not applicable for those interns that said they did not consume cocaine/base paste/crack)
Mode: 21 years

Inmates and children

63.9% of the inmates reported to have children (Table 18): 39% of the total of interns said they have one or two children (Table 19). Also, 15.8% have three or four children, and 9.2% of the inmates have five children or more. The mean is 1.7 children per inmate.

Additionally, when inmates were asked whether all of their children are from the same partner, 48.7% said they were by different partners (Table 20).

Table 18

Do you have any children?	
	Valid Percent
No	36.1%
Yes	63.9%
Total	100.0%

N = 367

Table 19

Number of children	
	Valid Percentage
None	36.1%
Between 1 and 2 children	38.9%
Between 3 and 4	15.8%
5 or more children	9.2%
Total	100.0%

N = 367

Table 20

Are all your children by the same partner	
	Valid Percent
Yes	51.3%
No	48.7%
Total	100.0%

N = 234

One every four inmates who have children (28.2%) had their first child before being eighteen or at eighteen years old (Table 21). More even, almost seven out of ten inmates (65.2 %) had their first child when they were twenty-one years old or less. These findings show that most inmates who have children had their first child at a relatively early age. Regarding the inmates' gender (Table 22), results show that women became parents at an earlier age than men: 54.2% of the women had their first child before being eighteen or at eighteen years old while this rate falls to 25.1% among men.

Table 21

At what age did you have your first child?		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-18	28.2%	28.2%
19-21	37%	65.2%
22-25	18.9%	84.1%
26 and more	15.9%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 234

(This question is not applicable to those inmates that said they have not children)

Table 22

"Age of the first child" and "Sex of inmate"				
		Sex of inmate		Total
		Male	Female	
Age of the first child	Up to 18	25.1%	54.2%	28.2%
	19 to 21	36.9%	37.5%	37%
	22 to 25	20.2%	8.3%	18.9%
	More than 25	17.7%	0%	15.9%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 234

Criminal background at the family

Six every ten inmates (56.9%) have a family member that has been in prison before (Figure 5). Of those who have someone in their family that has ever been sent to prison, 10.1% answered their father was sent to prison, and only 1.1% had their mother sent to prison (Figure 6). Additionally, 17.4% of the inmates had an uncle sent to prison, 17.2% had cousins sent to prison, and 23.7% had siblings or half-siblings sent to prison (Figure 7). Although these findings are not conclusive, they seem to suggest a link between family criminal background and inmates' personal involvement in crime.

Figure 5

Has anyone in your family ever been sent to prison?

N = 367

Figure 6

Who in your family has ever been in prison? Fathers and mothers

Multiple answers are allowed

Figure 7

Who in your family has ever been in prison? Other relatives

Multiple answers are allowed

Classmates

Four every ten inmates (39.6%) had classmates who had committed any crimes (Table 23). Although data are not conclusive, this result and those findings related with the inmates'

family history (above) seem to suggest that a criminogenic context influence in favor of criminal behavior.

Table 23

When you were in your last years in school, did you have any classmates who had committed any crimes, even if just one or several from time to time?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	39.6%
No	54.3%
DK/NA	6.1%
Total	100%

N = 367

Inmates' context before being arrested for the first time

The context in which the inmates lived before being arrested can be a factor that helps to explain why they were imprisoned. Violent social contexts might lead individuals to deviant behavior. Fights among neighbours and a low level of interpersonal trust in the neighborhood are often linked to criminal behavior. Low levels of economic satisfaction might be a cause for antisocial behavior. Contrarily to what could be expected, some findings suggest that this kind of context wasn't a cause of the inmates' arrest in Bahamas. For example, when inmates were asked how frequent were fights among neighbours in the place where they lived before they were arrested, a majority said that fights were not usual in their neighborhood: 47.5% of the inmates said that fights were "not frequent at all", and 19.3% said that fights were "not frequent". Additionally, the majority of inmates said that they trusted most of the people in their neighborhoods (54.7%) (Table 24 and Table 25).

Table 24

In the neighborhood where you lived before you were arrested, how frequent were fights among neighbors? Would you say that they were?	
	Valid Percentage
Very frequent	11.5%
Somewhat frequent	19.0%
Not frequent	19.3%
Not frequent at all	47.5%
DK/NA	2.8%
Total	100.0

N = 367

Table 25

Would you say that in the neighborhood where you lived before you were brought here you could trust most people? Or did you have to watch out for them?	
	Valid Percentage
You could trust most people	54.7%
You had to watch out for them	22.1%
Both	20.7%
Neither	0.8%
DK/NA	1.7%
Total	100.0%

N = 367

Regarding the geographical location of the inmates, when asked about where were they living when they got arrested, 72.7 % were living in New Providence, while 16 % in Grand Bahama, 3.3 % lived in Abaco, 2.5% in Andros, 1.9% in Eleuthera, and 3.6% in neither of these districts (Figure 8).

Figure 8

Where were you living when you were arrested?

N = 367

When it comes to the type of housing where they lived before being arrested, 63.7% reported they lived in a house, 32.8% in an apartment, 1.4% lived in a single room in a larger dwelling, 0.3% in a motor vehicle or boat, 0.3% lived on the street, 0.3% in an institution, and 1.4% in neither of these options (Figure 9). Contrarily to what could be expected, inmates living in

a poor type of housing before being arrested (*i.e.*, a single room in a larger dwelling, motor vehicle/boat, on the street, in an institution) are a small group.

Figure 9

Type of housing that best matches the one where you lived before your arrest for this offense

N = 367

Financial position, satisfaction with economic situation, and job status prior to arrest

Relative deprivation theory holds that individuals who perceive their own deprivation, relative to someone else, will feel frustration and injustice, and may attempt to ameliorate that feeling with deviant behavior (*i.e.*, Merton and Kitt 1950; Crosby 1976; Lopes 2008; Itashiki 2011).

The following questions ask for the level of satisfaction among inmates through different dimensions of welfare/deprivation perceptions or feelings, such as their financial position, economic situation, and job status. The hypothesis of a relative deprivation to explain criminal behavior seems to don't work in the Bahamas case: about 42.5% of the inmates felt that they were in a "better" or in a "much better" financial position than their immediate circle of friends before being arrested for the crime (Table 26). Also, 40.5% of the inmates felt in the "same" financial position of their friends, and only 9.8% and a 5.0% felt they were in a "worse" and "much worse" financial position respectively compared to their closer friends and relations.

Table 26

Just before your arrest for this crime, how would you describe your feeling towards your financial position compared to your immediate circle of friends and relations? Would you say that you felt you were:		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Much better off	7.5%	7.5%
Better off than most	34.9%	42.5%
About the same	40.5%	83.0%
Worse off than most	9.8%	92.7%
Much worse off than most	5.0%	97.8%
DK/NA	2.2%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

One month before being arrested for the crime, for which each inmate has been arrested, 62.7% of the respondents were “very satisfied” or “somewhat satisfied” with their economic situation and that of their family. Only the 17.2% of the inmates said that they were “very dissatisfied” with their own or their family’s economic situation (Table 27). Likewise, 71.8% of the inmates were “very satisfied” or “somewhat satisfied” with their family life one month before being arrested. Only the 10.7% of the inmates said they were “very dissatisfied” with their family life (Table 28).

Table 27

How satisfied were you with your economic situation and that of your family one month before you were arrested for this conviction?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Very satisfied	27.7%	27.7%
Somewhat satisfied	35.0%	62.7%
Somewhat dissatisfied	18.6%	81.4%
Very dissatisfied	17.2%	98.6%
DK/NA	1.4%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Table 28

How satisfied were you with your family life one month before you were arrested?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Very satisfied	46.3%	46.3%
Somewhat satisfied	25.4%	71.8%
Somewhat dissatisfied	16.1%	87.9%
Very dissatisfied	10.7%	98.6%
DK/NA	1.4%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

In other dimension of welfare/deprivation perception that was asked to inmates, satisfaction/dissatisfaction with their friends, 60.3% of the respondents said they were satisfied to some extent (“very satisfied” and “somewhat satisfied”) with them one month before being arrested for this crime. A small minority (9.6%) said that they were very dissatisfied with their friends (Table 29).

Table 29

How satisfied were you with your friends one month before you were arrested?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Very satisfied	27.2%	27.2%
Somewhat satisfied	33.1%	60.3%
Somewhat dissatisfied	12.2%	72.5%
Very dissatisfied	9.6%	82.2%
DK/NA	17.8%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

In the month before their arrest, 71.2% of the inmates were working and 28.8% were not working (Table 30). To the extent of which to have a job can be considered as an indirect indicator of subjective welfare (as opposed to have no job), this finding also seems to deny the relative deprivation theory. In other words, if the relative deprivation theory would work to explain criminal behavior, it should be found that the number of inmates not working in the month before their arrest (e.g., in condition of relative deprivation) should be higher than the number of inmates working the month before their arrest (e.g., in no condition of relative deprivation).² These results

² It is worthy to mention that when inmates were asked about their levels of satisfaction with their regular occupation or work one month before being arrested, 40.6% of the respondents said that they were “very satisfied” and the 26.6% said that they were “somewhat satisfied” with their regular

seem to deny a process of relative deprivation (e.g., persons without jobs) as the background to commit a crime.

However, when inmates' job conditions are taken into account, the picture is somewhat more complex. Thus, most inmates (68.1%) worked at that job between five and eight hours a day, that is, they worked following a regular workday (Table 31). However, 25.7% of the inmates said that they worked between nine and twelve hours a day, and 4.5% of the inmates said they worked at that job between thirteen and twenty-four hours a day. At the same time, 31.8% of the inmates said they used to work five days a week, that is, a regular working week. However, 15.9% of the inmates said to work six days a week, and 25% said to work seven days a week (Table 32). In the two latter cases, working weeks were exhausting for a large part of the inmates before being arrested. These findings talk about hard job conditions for a good portion of the inmates one month before they were arrested. Therefore, bad job conditions might be a path to commit a crime.

Table 30

In the month before your arrest, were you working?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	71.2%
No	28.8%
Total	100%

N = 367

occupation or work. But the 11.7% of the inmates were “somewhat dissatisfied” and the 18.6% were “very dissatisfied” with the work or regular occupation that they had one month before being arrested (see Appendix, Table 2).

Table 31

How many hours a day, in average, did you work at that job?		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-4	1.7%	1.7%
5-8	68.1%	69.8%
9-12	25.7%	95.5%
13-24	4.5%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 298

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that did not work previously to their arrest)

Table 32

How many days per week, on average, did you work at that job?		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1 day	2.3%	2.3%
2 days	4.5%	6.8%
3 days	6.8%	13.6%
4 days	13.6%	27.3%
5 days	31.8%	59.1%
6 days	15.9%	75%
7 days	25%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 298

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that did not work previously to their arrest)

It is important to analyze whether inmates received other income in addition to the salary from their jobs. This topic can be considered as a proxy to the economic situation of the inmates. Less than half of the inmates (45.5%) said that their salary was their only income. Regarding the types of incomes that inmates had one month before being arrested,³ 14.4% received another income for selling drugs, 10.1% received money from relatives, 5.2% received money from selling illegal goods, 4.4% received money from friends apart from their job income, and 1.4% received a

³ This indicator (other income/no other income) might be considered as a proxy of job conditions and, consequently, as a proxy of welfare/deprivation among inmates. The assumption is that if their incomes from their jobs were good (*i.e.*, satisfied their needs and/or expectations), inmates should not need other incomes. Those inmates with additional incomes (legal and, even more if illegal) suggest their incomes were not good (at least, in term of expectations).

pension or NIB (Figure 10). These findings show that a good portion of the inmates had incomes from both legal and illegal sources, and they suggest that inmates needed another income in addition to their job. Finally, 7.6% of the inmates said that they did not receive any income at all (Table 29). In summary, data suggests that job conditions were bad through different dimensions (hours of work per day, days of work per week, income) for a large percentage of inmates.

Figure 10

In the last month before you were arrested, apart from your jobs, what other income did you have?

Multiple responses are allowed
N = 367

Thus, questions on inmates' satisfaction with their economic situation, with their family life, with their friends, and with their regular occupation or work situation one month before being arrested (from Table 27 to Table 30) suggests that relative deprivation theory comes short to explaining criminal behavior among inmates in Bahamas. As it was mentioned above, relative deprivation is a condition in which injustice is perceived from a social comparison between what one has and what others have. It is theorized that relative deprivation –a perceived discrepancy between a current and expected situation– can lead to different strategies to adapt to this plight, including actual crime. This hypothesis seems to fail when it is applied to direct questions on satisfaction with different dimensions of the inmates' situation one month before being arrested (at least for a significant segment of the inmate population).

However, when inmates' job conditions are considered, the outlook seems to change. Bad job conditions can produce anger, resentment and aggression, and undermine commitment to social norms (Crosby, 1976; Reis, 1987). Findings using direct questions (i.e., satisfaction with inmates' situation) can be the result of a social desirability bias, that is, the fact that in self-

reports, people will often report inaccurately on sensitive topics in order to present themselves in the best possible light (Fisher 1993). Considering that procedures such as the use of indirect questions or proxy (*i.e.*, questions on objective job conditions) can be effective in preventing or reducing social desirability bias (Nederhof 1985; Schedler & Sarsfield 2007), we should not discard the relative deprivation theory to explain criminal behavior in the Bahamian case.

CHAPTER 2: CRIMINAL CAREERS AND INMATES' PROFILES: RECIDIVISM, VIOLENT CRIME, AND SERIOUS FELONIES

Sort of crime committed by the inmates

Regarding the type of crime, a good share of the interns is in prison for non-serious felonies. Thus, 20.4% of the inmates were arrested for drug possession or drug dealing. Also, 13.6% of the inmates are in prison for injuries. However, serious felonies also represent an important share of inmates: 14.2% of the interns committed intentional homicide and 22.1% are in prison for robbery or aggravated robbery. Other crimes, with different seriousness, were committed for a lower number of inmates: sex crime (6.8%), theft/aggravated theft (6.5%), manslaughter (6.5%), scam/misappropriation/fraud (4.6%), kidnapping (2.5%), and encroachment/identity theft (1.1%). Finally, extortion was committed for no inmates.

Figure 11

Crime for which you are now in prison

Multiple responses are allowed
N = 367

Regarding the type of crime by gender, findings show important differences between male and female inmates (Figure 12); men are more prone to serious felonies and women are more prone to non-serious felonies. Thus, 15.5% of the male are in prison for intentional homicide. This rate dramatically falls to 2.6% among females inmates. Also, 23.4% of the male inmates committed robbery or aggravated robbery while this rate is 10.5% in the female population in prison. This pattern seems to be confirmed when we compare male and female inmates in terms of their respective participation in non-serious felonies: the percentage of

women in prison tends to be similar (or higher) to the percentage of men for non-serious crimes. This is the case for scam/misappropriation/fraud and for drug possession/drug dealing. The higher percentage of female inmates can be observed with theft or aggravated theft: 10.5% of female versus 6.1% of the male. It's worth to mention other two findings: the percentage of female inmates that committed manslaughter is higher than the one for male inmates. Also, the percentage of men that committed injuries is lower than that of women.

Figure 12

N = 367

The first time for being arrested

When inmates were asked how old were they when they got arrested for the first time, one out of three (35.8%) said they were fifteen years or less. Also, 62.9% answered they were eighteen years old or less. Likewise, 82.1% of the inmates were twenty-one years old or less when they got arrested for the first time (Table 33). The mean was 17.85 years old, and the median was seventeen years old (Figure 13). All these findings show that most inmates began their criminal careers when they were young.

Table 33

How old were you when you got arrested for the first time?		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Up to 15 years	35.8%	35.8%
16 to 18 years	27.2%	62.9%
19 to 21 years	19.2%	82.1%
22 to 25 years	11.3%	93.4%
25 to 33 years	5.3%	98.7%
34 to 40 years	0.7%	99.3%
More than 40 years	0.7%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Figure 13

Frequency per age

N = 367

Mean = 17.85 years

Median = 17 years

Criminal Career and Recidivism

In terms of the percentage of inmates that committed recidivism, 44.5% of the inmates answered that they have been previously convicted for other crime, not including the one for which they are currently serving time (Table 34).

Table 34

Not including the crime for which you are currently serving time, have you been previously convicted of any other crime?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	44.5%
No	55.5%
Total	100.0%

N = 367

Of those who had already been convicted prior to their current conviction, 18.3% have been convicted for another crime only one time before the current arrest. This finding contrasts with those of most inmates: the majority of respondents said that they have been convicted many times before the current arrest. Thus, 50.0% have been convicted between two and five times, 10.6% have been convicted between six and nine times, 14.8% have been convicted between ten and fourteen times, and 6.3% have been convicted fifteen times or more (Table 35). These findings suggest that once an inmate is convicted once, it emerges a pathway of a criminal career that it is difficult to break.⁴

Table 35

How many times have you been arrested prior to this current conviction?	
	Valid Percent
1 time	18.3%
2 to 5 times	50.0%
6 to 9 times	10.6%
10 to 14 times	14.8%
15 or more times	6.3%
Total	100.0

N = 143

Alcohol or drugs and recidivism

Regarding the situational context of the offense, 6 of 10 (57.8%) of those inmates that were repeatedly offenders said to have used alcohol or drugs six hours before committing the

⁴ In this way, criminal behavior seems to be a path dependence phenomenon.

crime for which he or she is currently serving time (Table 36).⁵ The use of alcohol or drugs seems to influence the proneness to commit a crime again.

Table 36

“Use of alcohol or drugs six hours prior to the crime” and “Recidivism”				
		Recidivism		Total
		Yes	No	
Use of alcohol or drugs six hours prior to the crime	Yes	57.8%	45.8%	51.2%
	No	42.2%	54.2%	48.8%
Total		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

N = 367

Also, eight out of ten of those inmates (80.8%) that committed recidivism, had consumed illegal drugs at any time in his/her life (Table 37). Inmates that have ever consumed illegal drugs at any time in their lives seem to be more prone to commit recidivism.⁶

Table 37

“Have you ever consumed an illegal drug?” and “Recidivism”			
	Recidivism		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	80.8%	60.2%	69.3%
No	19.2%	39.8%	30.7%
Total	100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Criminogenic context during the childhood and recidivism

63.9% of those inmates that committed recidivism, said that when he or she were eighteen years old or less, she/he had friends that had committed any crime (Table 38). At the same time, the 60.8% of those inmates that didn’t commit recidivism didn’t have friends that had

⁵ This question does not mention if inmate had used alcohol or drug in his or her previous crime/s for which he or she is a recidivist. However, the question suggests a weak link between the use of alcohol or drugs and –at least, the last– crime.

⁶ If we consider this question as a proxy of addiction, findings suggest a relationship between addiction to alcohol or drugs and the proneness to commit recidivism.

committed any crime when they were eighteen years old or less. Having friends with any kind of criminal behavior at the inmates' childhood seems to be a strong predictor of recidivism (Table 38).

Additionally, 7 out of 10 (66.4%) of those inmates that committed recidivism, have lived as a minor in neighborhoods with gangs or criminal groups (Table 39). It is worthy to note that this percentage falls to 33.6% for inmates who committed recidivism and didn't live in neighborhoods with gangs or criminal groups. Both findings suggest that recidivism is related to an inmates' childhood criminogenic environment.

Table 38

		Recidivism		Total
		Yes	No	
Best friends committed any crime	Yes	63.9%	39.2%	50.2%
	No	36.1%	60.8%	49.8%
Total		100%	100.0%	100%

N = 367

Table 39

		Recidivism		Total
		Yes	No	
Gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where you lived as a minor	Yes	66.4%	47.1%	55.6%
	No	33.6%	52.9%	44.4%
Total		100%	100.0%	100%

N = 367

63.9% of those inmates that committed recidivism had a family member that served time in prison (Table 40). These findings suggest that an inmate with someone in the family that has been sent to prison is more likely to be a repeat offender.

Table 40

“Anyone in inmate’s family has been sent to prison” and “Recidivism”				
		Recidivism		Total
		Yes	No	
Anyone in inmate’s family has been sent to prison	Yes	63.9%	52.1%	57.4%
	No	36.1%	47.9%	42.6%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 367

54.4% of the inmates who recidivated also suffered violence at home when they were infants. In a more suggestive way, 63.3% of those inmates that didn’t commit recidivism reported they didn’t suffer domestic violence. Although findings are not conclusive, violence at home during childhood seems to be related with repetitive offenses and criminal careers (Table 41).

Table 41

“Violence in home” and “Recidivism”				
		Recidivism		Total
		Yes	No	
Violence in home	Yes	54.4%	36.7%	44.3%
	No	45.6%	63.3%	55.7%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 367

It seems there is no relationship between relative deprivation (the inmates’ own perceived situation compared with others) and recidivism. Those inmates that perceived they were “worst off than most” of the other people represent only the 15.6% of those that committed recidivism. Moreover, a good share of inmates that said they felt “better off than most” (35.7%) committed recidivism.

Table 42

"Recidivism" and "relative privation"			
	Recidivism		
Relative Privation	Yes	No	Total
Better off than most	35.7%	49.7%	43.4%
About the same	48.7%	36.2%	41.9%
Worst off than most	15.6%	14.1%	14.7%
Total	100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Violent crime

First of all, the level of violent crime among inmates (38.3%) is lower than the level of not violent crime (60.6%) as it is showed in Figure 14. Violence seems not to be a dominant trait of the crime among the inmates at Bahamas.

Figure 14

I am now going to ask you some questions about events at the time when you committed your crime. When such crime(s) occurred, were there people who suffered physical injury?

N = 367

In 6 out of 10 (60%) of those crimes where there were people who suffered physical injuries, the offender had used alcohol or drugs six hours prior to commit the crime (Table 43). Violent crime appears to be somewhat related to the use of alcohol and/or drugs during the six hours prior to commit the crime.

Table 43

“Use of alcohol or drugs six hours prior to the crime” and “Were there people who suffered physical injuries?”				
		Were there people who suffered physical injuries?		Total
		Yes	No	
Use of alcohol or drugs six hours prior to the crime	Yes	60.0%	45.5%	51.1%
	No	40.0%	54.5%	48.9%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 367

In 6 out of 10 (59.8%) of those crimes where there were people who suffered physical injuries, the offender lived as minor in neighborhoods with gangs or criminal groups (Table 44). Additionally, in 6 out of 10 (54.6%) of those crimes where there were people who suffered physical injuries, the inmate said that when he/she was eighteen years old or less, he/she have had friends that committed any crime (Table 45). Although these findings are not conclusive, violent crime seems to be related with inmates’ childhood into a criminogenic social context.

Table 44

“Gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where you lived as a minor” and “Were there people who suffered physical injuries?”				
		Were there people who suffered physical injuries?		Total
		Yes	No	
Gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where you lived as a minor	Yes	59.8%	52.4%	55.3%
	No	40.2%	47.6%	44.7%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Table 45

“Best friends committed any crime” and “Were there people who suffered physical injuries?”				
		Were there people who suffered physical injuries?		Total
		Yes	No	
Best friends committed any crime	Yes	54.6%	47.8%	50.4%
	No	45.4%	52.2%	49.6%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 367

In 6 of 10 (60.7%) of those crimes where there were people who suffered physical injuries, an inmate’s family member had been previously sent to prison (Table 46). This value falls to 39.3% among those inmates without anybody in their families with a criminal background. However, among those crimes where no people suffered injuries, the percentage of inmates with a criminal background in their families (55.4%) is also high. Findings in Table 5 however are not conclusive.

Table 46

“Anyone in inmate's family has been sent to prison” and “Were there people who suffered physical injuries?”				
		Were there people who suffered physical injuries?		Total
		Yes	No	
Anyone in inmate's family has been sent to prison	Yes	60.7%	55.4%	57.5%
	No	39.3%	44.6%	42.5%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 367

In eight of ten of those crimes where there were people who suffered physical injuries (76.7%), the inmate had consumed illegal drugs at any time in his/her life (Table 47). This value dramatically falls to only the 23.3% among the inmates who have not ever consumed an illegal drug. However, 64.7% of those offenders that did not use violence in their crimes, they have ever consumed an illegal drug. To having consumed an illegal drug is not clearly associated with violent crime.

Table 47

“Have you ever consumed an illegal drug” and “Were there people who suffered physical injuries?”				
	Were there people who suffered physical injuries?			Total
		Yes	No	
Have you ever consumed an illegal drug?	Yes	76.7%	64.7%	69.4%
	No	23.3%	35.3%	30.6%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Serious felonies

In this section, the report analyzes what factors are related with the commission of serious felonies. The first step is defining what types of crimes are considered serious felonies in this work. Although definitions may widely vary according different ethical, social, and legal considerations, in this report are defined as serious crimes intentional homicide/murder, manslaughter, kidnapping, extortion, sex crime, and robbery/aggravated robbery.

It is worth mentioning that serious felonies seem to be slightly related –at least compared to other violent crime– with the use of alcohol and drugs six hours prior to the crime. Hence, 54.5% of the inmates that committed a serious felony had used alcohol or drugs six hour prior to the crime (Table 48).

However, it seems there is a stronger relationship between those inmates that said they have ever consumed drugs and the commission of a serious felony. Table 49 show the percentage of those inmates that had ever consumed drugs among the inmates who committed a serious felony (74.5%) compared with the percentage of those inmates who had not consumed drugs (25.5%). In other words, almost eight out of ten inmates that committed a serious felony had ever consumed drugs at any time in their lives.⁷

⁷ It is worthy to note that a high percentage of inmates (62.2%) that had ever consumed drugs did not commit a serious felony (see Table 7a).

Table 48

"Use of alcohol or drugs six hours prior to the crime" and "serious felony/ non serious"				
		Serious felony		Total
		Yes	No	
Use of alcohol or drugs six hours prior to the crime	Yes	54.5%	45.9%	50.9%
	No	54.1%	45.5%	49.1%
Total		100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Table 49

"Have you ever consumed an illegal drug?" and "serious felony/ non serious"			
	Serious felony		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	74.5%	62.2%	69.4%
No	25.5%	37.8%	30.6%
Total	100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Also, it seems there is a –somewhat weak– relationship between serious felonies and inmates with friends at their childhoods that committed any crime: 53.3% of the inmates that committed a serious felony had friends with a criminal background when they were minors (Table 50).

Also, findings suggest that the commission of a serious felony as an adult is related to the presence of gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where inmates lived when they were minors (Table 51). Six out of ten of those inmates (58.6%) that committed a serious felony lived as minors in a neighborhood with criminal groups or gangs.

Table 50

"Best friends committed any crime" and "serious felony/ non serious"					
			Serious felony		Total
			Yes	No	
Best friends committed any crime	Yes		53.3%	45.3%	49.9%
	No		46.7%	54.7%	50.1%
Total			100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Table 51

"Gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where you lived as a minor" and "serious felony/ non serious"					
			Serious felony		Total
			Yes	No	
Gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where you lived as a minor	Yes		58.6%	50.3%	55.2%
	No		41.4%	49.7%	44.8%
Total			100%	100%	100%

N = 367

A similar result is found to the criminal background of the inmates' families. 57.6% of the inmates with anyone in their family that had been sent to prison committed a serious felony (Table 52). It would seem there is a somewhat weak relationship between inmates that committed a serious felony and families with a criminal history.

Table 52

"Anyone in inmate's family has been sent to prison" and "serious felony/ non serious"					
			Serious felony		Total
			Yes	No	
Anyone in inmate's family has been sent to prison	Yes		57.6%	56.9%	57.3%
	No		42.4%	43.1%	42.7%
Total			100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Concluding, the paths of criminal careers seem to be related with having lived in a criminogenic context during the inmates' childhood. For instance, having had friends with any kind of criminal behavior seems to be a strong predictor of recidivism. Also, having lived as a minor in neighborhoods with gangs or criminal groups is related with serious felonies. The situational context prior to the crime also matters. For example, violent crime appears to be related with the use of alcohol and/or drugs during six hours prior to commit the crime.

CHAPTER THREE: DUE PROCESS

Inmates' legal situation

The procedural situation of the inmates is mixed, although a vast majority of them are condemned inmates. Hence, seven out of ten inmates (68.4%) have already firm sentences, and will not file additional appeals; 16.1% will continue to appeal the sentence; 9.4% have been sentenced and neither them nor their lawyer have appealed the sentence. Finally, only the 0.3% of the inmates is going through trial, with no sentence yet (Figure 15).

Figure 15

N = 367

Time for the arrest

20.2% of the inmates were arrested within one hour after committing the offense for which they were charged with (Table 53). Moreover, 33.4% of the inmates were arrested during the same day of their offense. Most of these inmates were probably arrested “red-handed” or in flagrante. Also, almost six out of ten inmates (54.3%) were arrested into the first week after the alleged offenses were committed. On the contrary, 7.9% was arrested between six months and one year after the offense, and 5.3% were arrested more than one year after they committed their offense (Table 53).

Table 53

About how much time elapsed between when you committed the offense with which you were charged and when you were arrested?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Less an 1 hour	20.2%	20.2%
Between 1 hour and 3 hours	6.7%	27%
Between 3 hours and 1 day	6.5%	33.4%
Between 1 day and a week	20.8%	54.3%
Between one week and 1 month	14.7%	68.9%
Between 1 and 6 months	15.8%	84.8%
Between 6 months and a year	7.9%	92.7%
More an a year	5.3%	97.9%
DK/NA	2.1%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Police treatment

To the vast majority of the inmates (88.3%) the police never showed a warrant in writing. Only 9.7% of the respondents said they were shown a warrant when they were arrested (Table 54). Also, 90.9% of the inmates were taken to the police station after they got arrested (Table 55). Of those inmates that were taken to the police station, six out of ten interns (64.6%) were not informed at the police station that they were entitled to make a phone call: (Table 56). Additionally, one out of two inmates (47.6%) was not informed at the police station that they were entitled to a lawyer (Table 57). These findings suggest that police treatment to the inmates might have not fully protected the individual rights of the detainee.

A strong indication is the 42.8% of inmates that reported being hit or used physical force against them to compel them to testify or to change their statement while they were at the police station (Table 58). According to this finding, inmates' human rights were violated by the police in almost one out of two inmates.

Table 54

When you were arrested, did the police show you a warrant in writing?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	9.7%
No	88.3%
DK/NA	2.1%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 55

Were you taken to the police station after being arrested?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	90.9%
No	7.9%
DK/NA	1.2%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 56

While you were at the police station, were you informed that you were entitled to make a phone call (or communicate with someone you know)?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	34.1%
No	64.6%
DK/NA	1.3%
Total	100%

N = 334

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that were not in the police station)

Table 57

While you were at the police station, were you informed that you were entitled to a lawyer?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	52.4%
No	47.6%
Total	100%

N = 334

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that were not in the police station)

Table 58

Did anyone hit you or use physical force to compel you to testify or to change your statement while you were at the police station?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	42.8%
No	56.9%
DK/NA	0.3%
Total	100%

N = 334

(This question is not applicable those inmates that were not in the police station)

Finally, 57.6% of those inmates that were taken to the police station spent between three nights to one week at the police station, and 10.6% did so for more than one week (Table 59).

Table 59

How many nights did you spend in jail at the police station?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Did not spend the night	2.3%	2.3%
1 night	7.4%	9.6%
2 nights	21.2%	30.9%
More than 3 nights and less than 1 week	57.6%	88.4%
More than 1 week	10.6%	99%
DK/NA	1%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 334

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that were not in the police station)

Criminal justice treatment

Only 3.4% of the inmates were able to provide their statement to the magistrate the same day they arrived to the prison. Additionally, a vast majority of the inmates (67.5%) were able to provide their statement to the magistrate between one and five days after they arrived to prison. Other inmates had to wait more time: 15.7% did so between six and thirteen days after they arrived in prison, 3.7% took between two weeks and one month after their arrived prison, and 7.9% of the inmates gave their statement to the magistrate between more than one month and

almost a year. Finally, 1.9% of the inmates did so one year or more after they arrived to prison (Table 60).

Table 60

How long after you arrived in prison did you provide your statement to the magistrate?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Less than one day	3.4%	3.4%
1 to 5 days	67.5%	70.9%
6 to 13 days	15.7%	86.6%
2 weeks to 1 month	3.7%	90.3%
More than one month to less than one year	7.9%	98.2%
One year or more	1.9%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Regarding the preliminary statement as one dimension of due process, findings in Figure 16 are illustrative of some problems: in one out of two cases (48.0%), the magistrate was not present when the inmates made their preliminary statement. Also, in most of the cases (67.2%), the inmates' lawyer was not present when they made their preliminary statement. Additionally, six out of ten inmates (56.9%) were not informed they had the right to remain silent during their preliminary statement. Finally, 65.5% of the inmates were not informed during their preliminary statement that if they pleaded guilty they could get a reduced sentence.

Figure 16

During your preliminary statement...

N = 367

45.6% of the inmates or the inmates' lawyers requested bail (Table 61). Only three out of ten inmates (30.7%) were released on bail (Table 62).⁸

Table 61

Did you or your lawyer request bail?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	45.6%
No	51.2%
DK/NA	3.2%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 62

Were you released on bail?	
	Valid percentage
Yes	30.7%
No	67.5%
DK/NA	1.8%
Total	100%

N = 168

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that did not request bail)

⁸ Both questions "Did you or your lawyer request bail?" and "Were you released on bail?" were asked to the total of inmates.

Regarding how often the inmates met with their lawyers during the trial period, 21.9% of the respondents said they almost never saw them. Also, 11.2% of the inmates met their lawyers once a month. Contrarily, other inmates said that they met their lawyers almost daily (9.8%), other interns told once a week (8.6%), and others said every fifteen days (3.3%). Finally, a high percentage of respondents said “DK/NA” (20.7%) or “Other” (24.6%) (Table 64).⁹

Table 63

At that stage in the trial, how often did you see your lawyer?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Almost daily	9.8%	9.8%
Once a week	8.6%	18.4%
Every 15 days	3.3%	21.7%
Once a month	11.2%	32.9%
Almost never	21.9%	54.8%
Other	24.6%	79.4%
DK/NA	20.7%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

71.6% of the inmates reported that they were not transferred from one prison to another before they were sentenced on first instance (Table 64). Of those inmates who were transferred from one prison to another before being sentenced, 54.3% got farther away from where their families live after they were transferred. Also, 42.6% were at the same distance that before being transferred. Only 3.2% of the inmates got closer to where their families live (Table 65).

⁹ These high percentages for both categories might be indicating that inmates didn’t understand completely the question, particularly in relation to the period of reference (i.e., “at that stage in the trial”).

Table 64

Were you transferred from one prison to another before you were sentenced on first instance?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	27.2%
No	71.6%
DK/NA	1.2%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 65

After you were transferred, were you farther away or closer to where your family lives?	
	Valid Percentage
Farther	54.3%
The same	42.6%
Closer	3.2%
Total	100.0%

N = 99

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that were not transferred to other prison)

Regarding whether inmates understood what was happening at the hearings in court, 59.4% of the inmates said that they understood either “well” or “very well” what was happening at that moment (Table 66). However, 12.1% of the inmates said they understood “nothing”, 16.6% said “very little”, and 9.7% said “little”. If we add these percentages, 38.3% of inmates didn’t understand what was happening at the hearings in court. This is a problematic finding in terms of legal rights and due process. To perform an adequate defense, suspects should understand what is being claimed at the hearings in court.

Table 66

Thinking of the trial and all your hearings, how much did you understand of what was happening at the hearings and in court?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Nothing	12.1%	12.1%
Very little	16.5%	28.6%
A little	9.7%	38.3%
Well	15.9%	54.2%
Very Well	43.5%	97.7%
DK/NA	2.4%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

When inmates were asked about how many times they spoke directly to the judge, almost one third of them (28.2%) said they have never spoken to the judge directly. Also, 64.4% of inmates said they did so between one and five times, 4% of the inmates answered that they did so between six and ten times, and 3.4% said they spoke directly to the judge more than ten times (Table 67). However, when inmates were asked about how much they thought the magistrate listened to them, 23.8% of the respondents said “nothing”, 20.2% said the magistrate listened to them “very little”, and 10.1% said “little” (Table 68).¹⁰ These findings also suggest a problem of due process: half of the interns (54.1%) felt that the magistrate listened them little or even nothing.

Table 67

Number of times you spoke directly to the judge		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Never	28.2%	28.2%
1 to 5	64.4%	92.6%
6 to 10	4%	96.6%
More than 10	3.4%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

¹⁰ It is worthy to mention the high percentage of “DK/NA” responses, 18.8% (see Table 200). Considering the wording of this question, these responses might suggest that these inmates felt they were not listened.

Table 68

How much do you think the magistrate listened to you?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Nothing	23.8%	23.8%
Very little	20.2%	44%
A little	10.1%	54.1%
A lot	27.1%	81.2%
DK/NA	18.8%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Only 2.4% of the inmates received support from a human rights groups or organization between their arrest and the end of the trial (Table 69).

Table 69

During the period between your arrest and the end of the trial, did you receive any kind of support from any human rights group or organization?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	2.4%
No	95.5%
DK/NA	2.1%
Total	100%

N = 367

The number of lawyers that inmates had from their arrests to their sentences varied. It is worth to mention that 26.0% of the inmates didn't have a lawyer from their arrest until they were sentenced (Table 70). Thus, 45.1% of the inmates said that they had a private lawyer and 27.9% had a public lawyer (Figure 17). Also, a high percentage of inmates (27.0%) said DK/NA. This latter finding seems to indicate –again– a low level of understanding and knowledge among the inmates about the legal procedures and their actors.

Table 70

About how many lawyers did you have starting with your arrest and until you were sentenced?	
	Valid Percentage
No lawyer	26%
One lawyer	52%
Two lawyers	15%
Three to five lawyers	6.9%
Total	100%

N = 367

Figure 17

Was your main lawyer during the trial a public defender or a private lawyer?

N = 367

One out of two inmates (46.8%) think that their lawyers defended them “little” (10.6%), “very little” (23.0%) or “nothing” (13.3%). It is worthy to note that 27.2% of the inmates said “DK/NA”. These responses seem to confirm a finding mentioned above: a large segment of inmates didn’t understand what was happening throughout the judicial process.

Table 71

During the trial, how do you think your lawyer(s) defended you? If you had several lawyers, think of the most important		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Nothing	13.3%	13.3%
Very little	23%	36.3%
Little	10.6%	46.8%
Well	13%	59.8%
Very well	13%	72.8%
DK/NA	27.2%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Corruption and criminal justice

When inmates were asked whether any of the following public officials asked them for money or belongings since their arrest until their sentence, findings show a very low level of corruption among criminal justice personnel. Hence, a vast majority (97.0%) said the immigration officer did not do that. Also, 94.9% of the inmates said the prison staff did not ask them for money or belongings. Likewise, 97.6% of the inmates said the prosecutor did not ask them for money or belongings, and 98.5% said the magistrate did not ask them for that. Finally, and confirming a very low level of corrupt behavior among different criminal justice officers, 97% of the respondents answered that the court personnel did not ask them for money or belongings (Figure 18).

Figure 18

N = 367

CHAPTER FOUR: THE CONDITIONS IN THE PRISON

Accommodation and hygiene conditions

57.7% of the inmates answered that in prison they slept with more inmates that they should, given that cells are designed to accommodate a smaller number of people (Figure 19). Also, when asked if each of the inmates had a bed, 52.8 answered “Yes”, and 47% answered “No” (Table 72). When asked if last night they slept in a bed with a mattress only for themselves, the majority answered “No” (53.5%), and 46.5% answered “Yes” (Table 73). These findings seem to suggest that accommodation conditions are somewhat poor for a good share of the inmates.

Figure 19

Overcrowding

Table 72

And does each have a bed?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	52.8%
No	47.0%
DK/NA	0.3%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 73

Last night did you sleep in a bed with a mattress, only for yourself?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	46.5%
No	53.5%
Total	100%

N = 367

In order to learn on the accommodation and hygiene conditions supplied by the prison, inmates were also asked about who provides them certain items. These items include sheets, clothes, shoes, bed or mattress, toilet paper, soap, toothpaste and toothbrush. Only the 9% of respondents said that sheets were provided by the prison: 77.7% of the inmates said that sheets are provided by their family (Figure 20. When it comes to clothes, findings are relatively similar: 61.6% of the inmates are provided by their families whereas the 29.8% is provided by the prison (Figure 21).

Figure 20

N = 367

Figure 21

Clothes

N = 367

When inmates were asked about who provided them shoes, 82.3% said their family and only 6.1% said the prison (Figure 22). Also, for 62.1% of the inmates a bed or mattress was provided by the prison, although the 24.5% of the inmates reported that have not received a bed or mattress at all (Figure 23). In other words, one of every four inmates doesn't have either a bed or a mattress.

Figure 22

Shoes

N = 367

Figure 23

Bed or mattress

N = 367

When it comes to certain personal hygiene items, 98.8% of the inmates said they were being provided toilet paper. Also, 89.9% said they were being provided soap (Table 80). 84.1% of the inmates were being provided toothpaste, whereas the 67.7% were being provided toothbrush. These conditions seem to be better than what happens in other countries in Latin America and the Caribbean (Figure 24).¹¹

Figure 24

The prison provides you:

N = 367

¹¹ For a study of those conditions in Latin America and the Caribbean see, for instance, *Condiciones de vida en la cárcel. Resultados de la encuesta de detenidos condenados*, UNTREF, 2015.

When inmates are asked how many times per week they take a shower, 39.7% said they take from five to seven showers a week. Also, 27.6% of the inmates said they take between eight and fourteen showers a week. However, 28.2% of the inmates said they take between zero and four showers a week (Table 65).

Table 74

How many times a week do you take a shower?		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0 to 4 times	28.2	28.2
5 to 7 times	39.7	67.9
8 to 14 times	27.6	95.6
15 or more times	4.4	100.0
Total	100.0	

N = 367

Only 37.1% of inmates think the toilets that they use are either clean or very clean. Moreover, 26.3% of the respondents think the toilets they use are very dirty, and 17.8% believe that the toilets are dirty (Table 75). Also, 49% of the inmates said they have enough water to drink, but it tastes bad, and 11.9% of the interns think they don't have enough water to drink (Figure 25). Additionally, six out of ten inmates (59.1%) think the quality of the food they receive is very poor, and 32.7% thinks the food they receive is poor (Table 76). Finally, most of the inmates (60.7%) think that the amount of food they receive is not enough (Table 77).

Table 75

How clean are the toilets that you use?	
	Valid Percentage
Very clean	10.5%
Clean	26.6%
Dirty	17.8%
Very dirty	26.3%
DK/NA	18.7%
Total	100%

N = 367

Figure 25

Do you have enough water to drink?

N = 367

Table 76

Do you think that the quality of food you receive is?	
	Valid Percentage
Very good	.3%
Good	2.6%
Normal	5.5%
Poor	32.7%
Very poor	58.1%
DK/NA	.9%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 77

Do you think that the amount of food you receive is...?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Enough	35.8%	35.8%
Not enough	60.7%	96.5%
DK/NA	3.5%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Health care into the prison

The questionnaire includes a set of questions about the health care provided to the inmates by the prison. Findings are mixed. When inmates get sick, 76% of them receive medical care, and 19.7% do not (Table 78). However, only 13.8% are satisfied with the medical care

(“good” or “very good”) they receive when they get sick. Contrarily, 39.5% of the inmates consider the medical care as “poor” and 22.2% of the respondents consider it as “very poor” (Table 79).

Table 78

When you get sick, do you receive medical care?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	76.0%
No	19.7%
DK/NA	4.3%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 79

How would you rate the medical care you receive when you get sick?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Very good	3.8%	3.8%
Good	10%	13.8%
Normal	21.1%	34.9%
Poor	39.5%	74.3%
Very poor	22.2%	96.6%
When you get sick, you do not receive medical care	1.1%	97.7%
DK/NA	2.3%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

In most cases (80.9%), the prison provides the medicines the interns need. A small part of respondents said they obtained the medicines they need by other means: 6.3% ask other inmates for them, 1.4% of the inmates buys them with their own money (Table 94), 1.4% asks a family member , and 0.8% of the inmates have to steel them (Table 92). Finally, 4.4% of the inmates don't get the medicines they need, and 3.5% DK/NA (Figure 26).

Figure 26

How do you obtain the medicines you need?

N = 367

During their stay in prison, 74.3% of inmates got sick (Table 80). After the inmates were informed of their illness, 92.9% of the inmates continued to share the cell with inmates, and 4% were swop (Table 81). Also, 94.5% of the inmates said that HIV Aids tests were performed on them to verify whether they were infected or not (Table 82).

Table 80

During your stay in prison, did you ever get sick?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	74.3%
No	25.7%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 81

After you were informed of your illness, did you continue to share the cell with inmates?	
	Valid Percent
Yes	92.9%
No	4%
DK/NA	3.2%
Total	100%

N = 254

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that did not get sick)

Table 82

Did they perform any tests on you to verify whether you have HIV Aids?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	94.5%
No	2.8%
DK/NA	2.8%
Total	100%

N = 254

(This question is not applicable for those inmates that did not get sick)

Activities and entertainments into the prison

Also, the questionnaire includes a battery of questions about whether inmates have access to different types of entertainment. Findings are also mixed. On the one hand, most inmates (78.2%) have access to the radio, 89% of the respondents have access to a public phone, 69.4% have access to books, 66.3% of inmates have access to newspapers, and 54.5% have access to magazines. On the other hand, 57% of the inmates said that they cannot watch TV, and the vast majority of the inmates (98.8%) do not have access to a PC or the internet. The same happens with the access to a cell phone, although in this case due to security reasons: only the 4.4% of the inmate reported to have access to a cell phone (Figure 27).

Figure 27

You have access to:

N = 367

Treatment to relatives and economy of the visit to the prison

Keeping strong ties with families helps rehabilitation. The survey measured aspects of the relationship of inmates with their families. 26.2% of the inmates reported to have talked to their relatives every day. However, 18.2% of the respondents said they never talk to their relatives on the phone (Table 83). Also, during the three months previous to the interview, most of the inmates (55.2%) were visited by their families once a month. Contrarily, the 22.4% of the interns said that they never received a visit from their families in the last three months (Table 84).

Table 83

How often do you talk to your relatives on the phone?	
	Valid Percentage
Every day	26.4%
Twice a week	11.4%
Once a week	6.2%
Every 15 days	5.3%
Once a month	16.1%
Every 6 months	5%
Never	18.8%
Other	10.3%
DK/NA	.6%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 84

In the past 3 months, how often did your family visit you?	
	Valid Percentage
Every day of the week	.6%
Three times a week	.3%
Twice a week	.3%
Once a week	5%
Every 15 days	1.2%
Once a month	55.2%
Every 3 months	9%
Once a year	2.3%
Never	22.4%
Other	6.4%
DK/NA	.3%
Total	100%

N = 367

Four out of ten inmates (40.7%) think their relatives or partner are treated “so so” by prison personnel when they come to visit. Even more, 14.8% of the respondents think their relatives are treated “badly” and 5.6% of the inmates believe their families are treated “very badly” when they come to visit them. On the other hand, only 19.6% of respondents think their relatives or partner are treated either “well” or “very well” when they come to visit them. Finally, there is a high percentage of DK/NA: 19.3%. This finding seems to suggest that inmates prefer to say they don’t know or they simply don’t answer perhaps because of fear of reprisals (Table 85).

Table 85

How do you think your relatives or partner are treated when they come to visit you?	
	Valid Percentage
Very well	5.6%
Well	13.9%
So so	40.7%
Badly	14.8%
Very badly	5.6%
DK/NA	19.3%
Total	100%

N = 367

The inmates were also asked how much money do they spend in prison each month. The mean of these values was 165.7 dollars (Table 86).¹²

Table 86

How much do you spend in prison each month? (in dollars)		
	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0 to 50	37.7%	37.7%
51 to 100	22.8%	60.4%
101 to 200	20.6%	81%
More than 200	19%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Mean = 165.7 dollars

Corruption into the prison

The questionnaire has six questions asking for whether relatives, when they come to visit the inmates, they have to pay. These questions tap different dimension of corruption in the prison. Findings seem to support that there is no significant corruption in Bahama’s prison: 82.9% of inmates said their families didn’t have to pay for entering the prison, 73.6% said the inmates’ families didn’t have to pay for bringing them food , 69.5% of the relative did not have pay for conjugal visits, 79.2% of families did not have to pay for getting other items through, 81.0% of the relative did not have not to pay for bringing in work materials , and 77.0% of the inmates’ families did not have pay for bringing in forbidden items (Figure 28).¹³

¹² Although this question don’t permit to do an inference on this topic, maybe some of the inmates who spend more money are buying drugs.

¹³ It is worth to mention that, however, four out of the six questions have high levels of inmates responding DK/NA (29.6%, 16.3%, 18.4%, and 20.1% respectively). These high percentages of DK/NA, as in other questions below, might suggest fear of being punished among inmates due to their responses on this topic (corruption).

Figure 28

When your relatives come to visit, they do not have to pay for:

N = 367

Two additional questions inquire about fees and/or bribes from the authorities in the prison to the inmates' families. In this case, 93.2% of the inmates said they did not spend money on fees for the authorities, and only 6.8% said they did so (Table 87). When it comes to bribes for the authorities, 93.6% of the inmates said their families did not spent money on that, while 6.4% of them admitted to do so (Table 88).

Table 87

Fees for the authorities	
	Valid Percent
No	93.2%
Yes	6.8%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 88

Bribes for the authorities	
	Valid Percent
No	93.6%
Yes	6.4%
Total	100%

N = 367

Regarding the perceptions on corruption to obtain an undue pre-release, 42% of the interns think that no inmate has paid (bribed) to obtain a pre-release (Table 89). Contrarily, 26.2% of the inmates think other inmates/s have paid to obtain it. A large number of inmates (31.8%) said DK/NA. This is a very high percentage for DK/NA answers. These responses might be the result of asking a question on a very sensitive topic. In other words, these responses might result from the fear of some kind of consequences resulting from the disclosure of sensitive information.

Table 89

Do you think any inmate has paid to obtain pre-release?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	26.2%
No	42%
DK/NA	31.8%
Total	100%

N = 367

Conjugal visits and sexual life of inmates

Over the past six months, almost none of the inmates (89.2%) have received any conjugal visit (Table 90). According to the inmates, the main reason why this happened is because it was not permitted by the prison rules (51.8%).¹⁴ Other inmates said that they didn't receive any conjugal visit because they don't have a partner (25.1%). Also, 15.3% of interns answered that there is no infrastructure for that, 3.3% of the inmates said their partners don't come to visit, and 2% answered that the prison denied their request for conjugal visits. Finally, the 2.6% said DK/NA (Table 91).

¹⁴ It should be reminded that in most Latin American countries, conjugal visits, although regulated, are permitted under prison rules.

Table 90

Over the past 6 months, have you had any conjugal visit from your spouse or partner?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	1.2%
No	89.2%
DK/NA	9.6%
Total	100.0%

N = 367

Table 91

Why not?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
It is not permitted by the prison rules	51.8%	51.8%
I don't have a partner	25.1%	76.9%
There is no infrastructure for that	15.3%	92.2%
My partner doesn't come to visit	3.3%	95.5%
The prison denied my request for conjugal visits	2%	97.5%
DK/NA	2.6%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

When asked about whether in the past six months (prior to the interview) they have had sexual relations with any person other than their spouse or partner, a vast majority of the inmates answered “No” (96.5%). Only 1.2% of interns said they actually had sexual relations with someone else other than their spouse or partner, and 0.6% said they had sexual relations with a fellow prisoner. Finally, 1.8% of them said DK/NA (Table 92).

Table 92

During the past 6 months, have you had sexual relations with any person other than your spouse or partner?		
	Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Yes, with a fellow prisoner	0.6%	0.6%
Yes, with someone else	1.2%	1.8%
No	96.5%	98.2%
DK/NA	1.8%	100%
Total	100%	

N = 367

Most of the inmates (92.4%) said that since they were arrested, they have not witnessed another inmate being forced to have sexual intercourse with another person. On the other hand, 6.7% of the interns said they did witness a situation like the one just described, and 0.9% of the inmates said DK/NA (Table 93). In a similar way, 98.8% of the inmates said they were not forced to have sexual intercourse against their will since they were arrested (Table 94). In both cases, there are no important differences when females are compared with males.

Table 93

Since you were arrested, have you ever witnessed another inmate being forced to have sexual intercourse with other people?			
	Total	Male	Female
Yes	6.7%	7.0%	3.4%
No	92.4%	92.4%	93.1%
DK/NA	0.9%	0.6%	3.4%
Total	100%	100%	100%

N = 367

Table 94

Since you were arrested, have you ever been forced to have sexual intercourse against your will?			
	Total	Male	Female
Yes	,9	0.6%	3.6%
No	98,8	99.0%	96.4%
DK/NA	,3	0.3%	0.0%
Total	100,0	100.0%	100.0%

N = 367

Safety in prison

Inmates were asked about their perception and safety conditions in the prison facilities. Findings show the prison is roughly speaking an unsafe place for inmates. Firstly, eight out of ten inmates (80.2%) feel less safe in prison, compared to their home or the place where they lived before (Table 95).

Table 95

How safe do you feel here compared to your home or the place where you lived before?	
	Valid Percentage
Safer	4.9%
Just as safe	13.4%
Less safe	80.2%
DK/NA	1.5%
Total	100%

N = 367

While in prison, most of inmates (56.9%) said that someone has ever stolen their personal belongings (Figure 29).

Figure 29

While in prison, has anyone ever stolen your personal belongings?

N = 367

Regarding the personal safety of the interns, 25% of the inmates said that, in the past six months, they have been attacked or beaten (Table 96). However, this “picture” is very different when inmates are asked about whether they have seen *another* inmate being beaten: most of the inmates (84.3%) said “Yes” (Table 97). The difference between those responses might be the result of the difference between the uses of second-person vignette *versus* the use of third-person vignette in surveys. The second strategy has proved to be a useful practice for attenuating social desirability bias when surveys are used to ask sensitive topics (i.e., Tourangeau and Yan 2007).¹⁵ Therefore, the last finding should be considered more reliable than the first one. In other words, violence seems to be an important problem in the prison.

Table 96

In the past 6 months, have you been attacked or beaten?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	25%
No	75%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 97

Have you seen other inmates being beaten?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	84.3%
No	15.7%
Total	100%

N = 367

Alcohol and drugs inside the prison

When inmates were asked if during the past month they have used alcohol and/or drugs, 26.8% of the inmates said yes (Table 98). As seen above following other questions, these responses are different when the questionnaire uses third-person vignettes. In the latter case, most of the inmates (65.6%) have seen other inmates using alcohol and/or drugs (Table 99). Since this is a sensitive topic, we should consider the second question more valid as a proxy to the extent of use of alcohol and/or drugs inside prisons.

¹⁵ It is worthy to note that recent research has found that within an experimental framework (i.e., the use of survey experiments) there is little difference between the response patterns in sensitive topics for the third-person vignette as compared to the second-person vignette (Winters & Weitz-Shapiro 2013).

Table 98

During the past month, have you used alcohol and/or drugs?	
	Valid Percent
Yes	26.8%
No	73.2%
Total	100.0%

N = 367

Table 99

Have you seen other inmates using alcohol and/or drugs?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	65.6%
No	33.8%
DK/NA	0.6%
Total	100%

N = 367

To explore the type of drugs and substances consumed inside the prison, we ask questions about this topic using in the third-person vignette. Findings show that of those who saw other inmates using alcohol or drugs, 23.2% saw that they were drinking alcohol. Considering the use of drugs, 61.0% saw that they were consuming marijuana, 2.7% were taking pills. 2.5% were using cocaine, base paste or crack, and 1.4% were using other drugs. These findings suggest that the use of alcohol and soft drugs prevails over the use of hard drugs into the prison.

Figure 30

Getting drugs and substances

Half of the inmate population (52%) thinks it is either “very easy” or “easy” to get drugs and substances (Table 100). This indirectly supports the assumption that drugs circulate widely. Additionally, there is a high percentage of inmates that said “DK/NA” (17.9%).

Table 100

According to your knowledge, to get drugs and substance in prison is:	
	Valid Percentage
Very easy	18.2%
Easy	33.8%
Difficult	15.3%
Very difficult	14.7%
DK/NA	17.9%
Total	100%

N = 367

According to inmates’ responses, a vast majority (65.8%) believes that the prison staff brings more drugs into prison (Figure 31). Also, 4.2% of the inmates think police officers or guards participate in this smuggling and only the 1.4% of respondents believe that enforcement officers are who gets more drugs for the inmates. Finally, the 3.9% believes relatives or visitors are those who bring more drugs into the prison (Figure 31). These findings imply that the majority of the inmates think that there are public officers involved in the distribution of drugs into the prison. It is worthy to mention again the very high percentage of DK/NA responses: one out of four inmates said they didn’t know or they didn’t response (it can be suggested that high responses of DK/NA might be an effect caused by fear).

Figure 31

Activities and programs for social reintegration in the prison

25.9% of the inmates think that the education programs that the prison provides are either “good” or “very good”. 7.8% and 7.3% believe the programs are “poor” or “very poor” respectively. Only 3.8% of the inmates said they did not attend any education programs, although the 42.2% said DK/NA (Table 101). This very high value for DK/NA might tell that a large part of inmates did not participate in these programs.

Table 101

How would you rate the education programmes that the prisons provide? Do you think they are...?	
	Valid Percentage
Very good	11.6%
Good	14.2%
Normal	13.1%
Poor	7.8%
Very poor	7.3%
Do not have any	3.8%
DK/NA	42.2%
Total	100%

N = 367

Only 14.0% of the inmates are satisfied (“very good” and “good”) with the assistance given by psychologists and social workers in the prison (Table 102). As in the former case of the education programmes, findings show a very high percentage of inmates responding DK/NA (44.5%).¹⁶

Table 102

How do you rate the assistance given by psychologists and social workers in the prison? Do you think it is..?	
	Valid Percentage
Very good	4.7%
Good	9.3%
Normal	6.1%
Poor	7.8%
Very poor	11.3%
We don't have such assistance	16.3%
DK/NA	44.5%
Total	100%

N = 367

¹⁶ Other hypothesis to explain the very high level of DK/NA responses might be that to extent in which the inmates’ responses might be interpreted as an evaluation of the personnel performance, these topics would induce to respondents to choose strategically to avoid an explicit answer. However, the low level of participation in such programs that other questions show, it lead to interpret those DK/NA responses in this case has to do with a very low level of knowledge on these programs among inmates.

Regarding the inmates' participation in different kind of educational and entertainment activities in the prison, findings show inmates participate at low rates. Hence, only 26.3% of the inmates have participated in sports activities, and only the 31.1% have participated in educational activities. Moreover, only 22.5% have participated in entertainment activities. Additionally, 38.1% of the inmates did learn any trade in prison, whereas the 61.4% did not (Figure 32).

Figure 32

Participation in activities inside the prison

N = 367

Other aspects of the inmates' everyday life are related to whether they do any work inside the prison, what kind of work they do or what are the condition of that work. 57.6% of the inmates perform some kind of work inside the prison (Table 103).

Table 103

Do you perform any work inside the prison?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	57.6%
No	42.4%
Total	100%

N = 367

The kinds of work they do is as follows: 20.7% of the inmates do prison maintenance work, 14.4% did prison cleaning work, 7.6% did other labor activities, 7.1% did craftsmanship, and 12.8% did other types of job (Figure 33).

Figure 33

N = 367

In contrast to the perceptions of the entire inmate population, those interns that did participate in educational activities (N = 105), had positive opinions about these activities: 55.2% of this group of inmates thought that in the classes they took in prison, they have learned “very much” and 31.4% believed that they have learned “enough” (Table 104). Moreover, a vast majority of the inmates (Table 105) thought that once they will be released, what they studied in prison will be either “useful” (44.8%) or “very useful” (48.6%).

Table 104

Do you think that in those classes you learn?	
	Valid Percentage
Very much	55.2%
Enough	31.4%
Little	7.6%
Nothing	3.8%
DK/NA	1.9%
Total	100%

N = 105

(This question does not apply to inmates that did not participate in classes in the prison)

Table 105

Do you think that, once you are released, what you study in the prison will be?	
	Valid Percentage
Very useful	48.6%
Useful	44.8%
Not useful	4.8%
Not useful at all	1.9%
Total	100%

N = 105

(This question does not apply to inmates that did not participate in classes in the prison)

Beyond the prison: life after being released

41.2% of the inmates said they already have a job waiting for them, once they are released from prison. Also, 20.3% said they will apply for a job related to their trade or occupation, 17.4% will apply for any type of job, and 6.2% will look for a job among their acquaintance or relatives. Additionally, 5.3% don't know where are they planning to work, and 3.8% haven't thought about it yet (Figure 34).

Figure 34

Where are you planning to work?

N = 367

When inmates were asked about their life after prison, the findings are mixed. Most inmates are optimistic when asked about how they think things will go for them after their release

compared with the situations they lived before the last time they were arrested. 72.3% of the inmates think that their lives will go better for them after they are released from prison. 17.6% believes that things will be the same. Only 3% thinks things will be worse once when they are released (Table 106).

Table 106

How do you think things will go for you after you are released compared to your situation before the last time you were arrested?	
	Valid Percentage
Better	72.3%
The same	17.6%
Worse	3%
DK/NA	71%
Total	100%

N = 367

However, most inmates (70.9%) are afraid of at least three of these obstacles upon release: housing, jobs and family (Table 107). 40.3% of inmates are afraid that after being released will not be able to find a job, 21.3% are afraid their families will reject them, and 9.3% are afraid of not having a place where to live.

Also, when inmates were asked about whether they were afraid of other four options (Table 108), most of them (75.6%) were afraid of: being arrested again (42%), getting sick or developing an addiction (16.1%), being killed because of what they did (11.2%), and being attacked or hurt (6.3%).

Table 107

Of these three options, What are you most afraid of after your release?	
	Valid percentage
Not having a place where to live	9.3%
Not finding a job	40.3%
My family rejecting me	21.3%
Not afraid	29.1%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 108

Of these four options, What are you most afraid of after your release?	
	Valid percentage
Being attacked or hurt	6.3%
Getting sick or developing an addiction	16.1%
Being arrested again	42%
Being killed because of what I did	11.2%
Not afraid	24.4%
Total	100%

N = 367

When inmates were asked using a direct question about their chances of being arrested again, most inmates were optimistic: the vast majority of the inmates (75.5%) believed that the likelihood of being re-arrested is “most probably not” and 17.1% thought that is “probably not” (Table 109). In sum, more than 90% believed that they will not be re-arrested.

Table 109

How likely do you think you are of being arrested again? Do you think you'll be rearrested?	
	Valid Percentage
Most probably yes	0.3%
Probably yes	3.5%
Probably not	17.1%
Most probably not	75.5%
DK/NA	3.5%
Total	100%

N = 367

Inmates have very little knowledge about government agencies that provide some sort of support (helping find a job, housing etc) at the re-entry phase. Only 16.3% of the inmates said they did know of government departments (Table 110). Also, when it comes to civil society

groups that help people coming out of jail to find a home and a job during the first months after their release, only 34.4% of the inmates reported to be aware of such groups (Table 111).

Table 110

Do you know whether there are any government departments that help people coming out of jail to find a home and a job during the first months after their release	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	16.3%
No	69.8%
DK/NA	13.9%
Total	100%

N = 367

Table 111

Do you know any civil society groups such as churches, human rights organizations or special groups that help people coming out of jail to find a home and a job during the first months after their release?	
	Valid Percentage
Yes	34.4%
No	54.6%
DK/NA	11%
Total	100%

N = 367

FINAL REMARKS

The types and dynamics of the inmates' household during their childhood proved to be important. Inmates emerge from childhood homes where adult male figures are missing, where violence is usual and adults participate in activities that might be a cause of deviant behavior. In many cases, adult female figure were also absent during the interns' childhood. Many inmates' mothers needed to work in time-demanding and lower incomes jobs. A vast majority of the inmates said they were physically punished by either their parents or guardians. Also, in many of the inmates' households the father or the mother's partner had beaten her/his mother. This kind of dynamic could contribute to a low level of social control at home when inmates were children.

Also, findings in our study indicate that a large share of inmates lived in a criminogenic territorial context when they were children. Many of them had friends that had committed any crime when those were kids. Additionally, a majority of the inmates said there were gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where they grew up. Most inmates had a family member that had been sent to prison when they were children. In brief, findings suggest a harsh early life for most inmates either in their households or in their communities. Such childhood environment may have contributed to the development of criminal behavior.

The inmates' life stories suggest a complex set of great hardship and a very limited structure of opportunities. Most inmates had to start to work at an early age: many interns worked for the first time when they were only twelve years old or less and half of inmates had to start working when they were fifteen years old or less. Moreover, most of the inmates left school at a premature age. The highest level of education reached before being arrested for the first time was incomplete high school or lower. A large share of inmates left school at a premature age. Other limiting pattern is that most inmates were very young when they had their first child. These living conditions among a good part of the prisoners from an early age may have led them to antisocial behavior.

Regarding the context of the inmates before being arrested, this report finds several relevant results. As it is well-known, the context in which the inmates lived before being arrested usually is a factor that helps to explain why they were imprisoned. For instance, violent social environments might lead to individuals to deviant behavior: fights among neighbours and a low level of interpersonal trust in the neighborhood are often linked to criminal behavior. In contrast to what might be expected, findings suggest that this kinds of contexts weren't a cause for the

inmates' arrest. For example, most inmates said that fights were not usual in their communities and the majority of inmates said that they trusted most of the people in their neighborhoods.

Moreover, relative deprivation theory doesn't fully explain criminal behavior in the Bahamas. Most inmates felt that they were in a "better" or in a "much better" financial position than their immediate circle of friends before being arrested. Likewise, most respondents were "very satisfied" or "somewhat satisfied" with their economic situation and that of their family.

When we compare the findings for the context and the situation previous to the arrest of most inmates with the results in the context during the inmates' childhood, it seems that infancy is much more important than the context in which the inmates lived before being arrested to explain antisocial behavior. However, inmates' job conditions before being arrested seem to be an exception into this general rule: workdays and working weeks were exhausting for a large share of the inmates before being arrested. In other words, although most inmates were working, results show hard job conditions for a good portion of the inmates one month before they were arrested.

Regarding the inmates' profiles in terms of their criminal careers, findings in this report show that most inmates were arrested for the first time when they were very young. Also, almost half of the inmates are repeat offenders. Moreover, the majority of inmates were convicted many times before the current arrest. It seems that most inmates began a criminal career once they were arrested for the first time. Thus, findings suggest that once an inmate is convicted one time, it emerges a pathway of a criminal career that is difficult to break. However, it's worth to note that since the survey was applied to a sample of inmates, we don't have in our population individuals released in the past who didn't commit recidivism. For this reason, findings supporting the hypothesis of an *inevitable pathway* to a criminal career might be biased by the very population being studied in this report, that is, inmates in prison.

The factors that lead to recidivism are many. Recidivism seems to be related with the consumption of illegal drugs, with a family where someone was sent to prison, and with violence at home during the inmates' childhood. Also, friends' with any kind of criminal behavior at the inmates' childhood seems to be a predictor of recidivism. Therefore, recidivism seems to be related with an inmate's childhood developed in a criminogenic context.

Regarding violent crime, violence does not seem to be a dominant trait of the crime among the inmates at Bahamas. However, the comparative low level of violent crime seems to be

related to the use of alcohol and/or drugs during the six hours prior to the commission of the crime. Violent crime also seems to be related with inmates' childhood in a criminogenic social context.

Considering serious felonies, findings suggest that there is a relationship between inmates who committed a serious felony and families with a criminal background. Also, it seems that to commit a serious felony as an adult is related with the presence of gangs or criminal groups in the neighborhood where the inmates lived when they were minors. As in the case of violent crime, serious felonies also seem to be related with inmates' childhood in a criminogenic social and family context.

Regarding the due process, and focusing on police action and treatment, results in this report suggest some problems in terms of due process in the Bahamas. A good share of inmates' answers outlines a picture in which civil rights are not respected. From the right to be shown a warrant in writing by the police to the more basic human right of non violence from the state, due process seems to be somewhat weak when police behavior is analyzed.

This report also founded important results on other topics of the due process such as the criminal justice treatment. On the one hand, many inmates were abandoned to their fate: neither the magistrate nor the inmates' lawyer was present when they made their preliminary statement in a good share of the cases. On the other hand, many inmates faced informational problems: most interns were not informed that they had the right to remain silent or that they had the right to plead guilty that could get them a reduced sentence during their preliminary statement. Findings also show that a good share of inmates neither understood what was happening at the hearings in court nor have spoken to the judge directly. More disturbing, one out of four inmates didn't have a lawyer from their arrest until they were sentenced. All these aspects of the criminal justice treatment mean a weakening of the right to proper defense. Of course, these are the "voices" of the inmates that may have not been reported accurately. Yet, these large rates signals that indeed many of these findings are probably correct.

Prison conditions were also analyzed in this report. When inmates were asked who provided certain items to them for their accommodation and their hygiene such as sheets, clothes, shoes, bed or mattress, toilet paper, soap, toothpaste and toothbrush, findings suggest that most of the goods for the inmates were provided by their families and not by the prison. Also, many inmates think the toilets they use are either dirty or very dirty. Also, a large majority of inmates affirm that the quality of the food they receive is poor or very poor. Also, most of the

inmates believe that the amount of food they receive is not enough. Half of the inmates thinks that the water they receive is enough but it tastes bad.

Regarding the health care provided by the prison, findings are mixed. When inmates get sick, most of them receive medical care, although only few inmates are satisfied with it. However, in most cases, the prison provides the medicines the inmates need.

Considering the access to different types of entertainment, findings are also mixed. Most inmates have access to the radio, to a public phone, books, newspapers, and magazines. However, most inmates said that they cannot watch TV, and the vast majority of the inmates said they do not have access to a PC or to the internet.

Findings also seem to support that there is no corruption in the prison: consistently, a vast majority of inmates said their families don't have to pay for entering the prison, for bringing them food, nor for conjugal visit, for getting other items through, for bringing in work materials, neither for bringing in forbidden items. Similarly, and regarding the perceptions on corruption to obtain an undue pre-release, a large share of the inmates think that no inmate has paid to obtain a pre-release.

When inmates were asked about their perceptions on their safety conditions in the prison, a large share of inmates feel less safe at prison compared to their home or the place where they lived before. Also, while in prison, most of the inmates said that someone has ever stolen their personal belongings. Additionally, eight out of ten inmates said they have seen another inmate being beaten. However, and considering the risk of having sexual intercourse against their will, a large majority said that neither themselves were forced nor witnessed another inmate being forced to have sexual intercourse with another people. In this regards, there is no difference between female inmates and male inmates.

In terms of addictions, a large share of inmates said they had seen other inmates using alcohol and/or drugs. Regarding the kinds of the substances that inmates consume, findings suggest that the use of alcohol and soft drugs prevails over the use of hard drugs into the prison. In the same vein, half of the inmates think it is either "very easy" or "easy" to get drugs and substances. With implications in terms of policy, many inmates believe that the prison staff is who brings more drugs into the prison.

Regarding activities oriented to the social reintegration of the inmates, few inmates think that the education programs that the prison provides are either "good" or "very good". Also, few

interns are satisfied with the assistance given by psychologists and social workers in the prison. Inmates' participation in entertainment activities in the prison –such as sport activities –, is low. Somewhat differently, six out of ten inmates perform some kind of work inside the prison.

Considering inmates' life after prison, most interns are optimistic when they are asked about how they think things will go for them after they are released: most inmates think that their lives will go better for them after prison. However, most inmates are also afraid of some issues. Among these issues, many inmates are afraid of not finding a job, being rejected by their families, being arrested again, getting sick or developing an addiction. More worrying, few inmates have knowledge on governmental departments that helps people coming out of jail to find a job and a home. These findings have important implications in terms of policy. On the one hand, released inmates require support from specific programs and governmental agencies. On the other hand, if these programs and agencies already exist, they should make an effort to communicate.

APPENDIX

Data collection started on June 9th and ended on June 24th, 2016. A total of 367 inmates (329 males and 38 females) were interviewed. A list of inmates, dated the 10th May 2016, was used to design the sample. The list indicated 31 females and 983 male. The study attempted to sample 100% of the female inmate population and 27.4% of the male inmate population. The sample of males was randomly selected to reflect the percentage of this subpopulation in various security areas of the prison. However, some of the inmates did not wish to participate in the survey and the inmate population varied from day to day. Consequently, in addition to the random selection of “first choice” inmates, a second randomly selected list of replacements was drawn up to allow changes in the prison population and because of the fact that not all inmates on the first choice list might wish to participate. As a result, we introduce adjustments to the sample. The rejection rate was 81.7%.

Prior to the interview, each selected inmate was informed about the purpose of the interview and asked to sign a consent form. Participation was entirely voluntary and no inducements were offered. Data collectors signed a confidentiality form with the Parole Commission stating that the information provided by the inmates would be held in confidence and the information collected would be discussed with the Parole and Probation Committee and research group only.

As not all surveys were completed, this represents the maximum sample size.¹⁷ The additional interviews (beyond 300) were undertaken to ensure that as close as possible to 300 interviews were completed. The final sample also reflects the dynamic nature of the prison population as more than the anticipated number of female inmates were interviewed (Fielding & E'Thegra Symonette, 2016).

The paper questionnaire was loaded onto Survey Monkey with slight modifications to account for the logical skips required in the questionnaire. Some question permitted multiple responses. Therefore, in some cases, the number of responses naturally exceeds the number of inmates responding. Further, in some cases, percentages in tables may not sum to 100% due to rounding errors.

¹⁷ There were some technical limitations of the fieldwork in Bahamas such as “Internet connection was interrupted on at least one occasion which resulted in lost responses” (Fielding & E'Thegra Symonette, 2016:2).

TABLES

Table 1

"During that period did your parents live together?" and "serious felony/non serious"				
		Serious felony - non serious felony		Total
		Yes	No	
During that period did your parents live together?	Yes	43.7%	46.1%	44.7%
	No	56.3%	53.9%	55.3%
Total		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Table 2

How satisfied were you with your regular occupation or work situation one month before you were arrested?			
		Valid Percentage	Accumulated Percentage
Valid	Very satisfied	40,6	40,6
	Somewhat satisfied	26,6	67,1
	Somewhat dissatisfied	11,7	78,9
	Very dissatisfied	18,6	97,4
	DK/NA	2,6	100,0
	Total	100,0	

REFERENCES

Crosby, F. J. (1976). A model of egotistical relative deprivation. *Psychological Review*, 83: 85–113.

Fielding & Symonette, E. (2016). *Summary of a 2016 Study of Sentenced Inmates in The Bahamas*. The Bahamas Department of Correctional Services and The College of Bahamas: Nassau.

Fisher, R. J. (1993). "[Social desirability bias and the validity of indirect questioning](#)". *Journal of Consumer Research*, 20: 303-315.

Itashiki, Michael Robert (2011). *Explaining "Everyday Crime": A Test of Anomie and Relative Deprivation Theory*. University of North Texas. Dissertation Prepared for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy.

Karstedt, S. & Farrall, S. (2006). The moral economy of everyday crime: Markets, consumers and citizens, *British Journal of Criminology*, 46: 1011–1036.

Lopes, C.A. (2008). *Economic development and consumer morality*. Paper presented at International Conference on Survey Methods in Multinational, Multiregional, and Multicultural Contexts , Berlin, Germany.

Merton, R. K., & Kitt, A. S. (1950). Contributions to the theory of reference group behavior. In R. K. Merson & . F. Lazarsfeld, (Eds.), *Continuities in social research*, pp. 40–105. Glencoe IL: The Free Press.

Minnis, J. Stevenson M., Symonette, E., & Gibson T. (2012). *A profile of the sentenced inmate at Her Majesty's Prison, Fox Hill, Nassau, Bahamas*: The College of Bahamas.

Nederhof, A. J. (1985). "Methods of coping with social desirability bias: a review" in *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 15: 263-280.

Schedler, A. & Sarsfield, R. (2007). "Democrats with adjectives: Linking direct and indirect measures of democratic support", *European Journal of Political Research*, 46(5): 637–659.

Tourangeau, Roger, & Ting Yan (2007). "Sensitive Questions in Surveys", *Psychological Bulletin* 133(5): 859–83.

Winters, M. & Weitz-Shapiro, R. (2013). "Third-Person versus Second-Person Vignettes in Survey Experimental Research on Sensitive Topics". Manuscript.